
Informal Sector and Community Development in Oyo Town, Oyo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The informal sector plays a crucial role in community development by providing employment, fostering entrepreneurship and contributing to economic resilience. This study examined the influence of the informal sector on community development in Oyo Town, Oyo State. By assessing the contributions of informal businesses to local economic activities and social cohesion, the research revealed the sector's significant role in combating unemployment and fostering entrepreneurship among youth and adults. Using a mixed-methods approach, data were collected from 150 informal sector operators across four local government areas through structured questionnaires. Key findings indicated that while the informal sector contributes to income generation and enhances local livelihoods, challenges such as limited access to finance, governmental regulations and infrastructural inadequacies hinder its growth and sustainability. Correlation analysis indicates a strong positive relationship ($r = 0.63$) between business growth and loan access, underscoring the critical need for financial inclusion. Additionally, a moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.52$) between business growth and income levels suggests that expanding enterprises enhance household earnings. Conversely, a strong positive correlation ($r = 0.72$) between unemployment and social vices highlights that rising joblessness contributes to increased crime rates. The researchers recommended improved financial inclusion, infrastructure development, and vocational training initiatives to enhance the informal sector's contribution to sustainable community development.

Keywords: Informal Sector, Community Development, Employment Generation, Skill Acquisition, Economic Empowerment

Introduction

The informal sector plays a significant role in the economy of developing countries, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa, including Nigeria (Onokerhoraye, 1977). It encompasses a wide range of economic activities that operate outside formal regulations, including petty trade, street vending, artisanship, transportation services, and small-scale manufacturing. According to the International Labour Organisation (ILO), the informal

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sector accounts for over 80% of employment in sub-Saharan Africa, making it a crucial source of livelihood for millions of people.

In Nigeria, the informal economy contributes significantly to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and employment, particularly in urban and peri-urban areas where formal job opportunities are limited. The sector provides essential goods and services, fosters entrepreneurship, and enhances local economic resilience. Many micro and small enterprises (MSEs) in the informal sector serve as an entry point for employment, particularly for women and youth, who often face barriers to accessing formal jobs. Despite its importance, the informal sector faces numerous challenges, including lack of access to credit, inadequate infrastructure, regulatory constraints, and social protection deficits. Workers in the sector often operate under precarious conditions, with little or no job security, health benefits, or legal protections. Furthermore, urban planning policies sometimes marginalised informal workers, leading to evictions, market demolitions, and restricted access to public spaces. The informal sector in Nigeria encompasses a wide range of economic activities that operate outside the formal regulatory framework (Ikadeh, 2020). These activities include petty trading, street vending, transportation services (such as motorcycle taxis and minibuses), home-based enterprises, small-scale manufacturing, and artisanal services. Informal employment is particularly prevalent in urban centres like Lagos, Ibadan, and Kano, where a significant portion of the population relies on daily income from self-employment and unregistered businesses.

These activities are often characterised by small-scale operations, low capital investment, and a lack of formal registration or regulation (Onokerhoraye, 1977). Many informal enterprises operate from temporary or mobile locations, with limited access to infrastructure such as electricity, water and proper market spaces. Workers in this sector typically lack job security, health benefits and pension schemes, making them vulnerable to economic shocks. Despite these challenges, the informal economy remains a critical driver of employment, particularly for low-income households, women, and youth who face barriers to entering the formal labour market.

Hart's study in Accra introduced the concept of formal and informal income opportunities, distinguishing between wage-earning and self-employment (Onokerhoraye, 1977). Regionally, the structure and scale of informal activities vary significantly. In urban areas, commercial hubs like Lagos and Ibadan have vibrant informal economies with extensive networks of street traders, transport operators, and artisans. In contrast, rural informal economies often revolve around agriculture, food processing, and handicrafts. Additionally, cross-border trade is a key aspect of informal economic activity, particularly in border states like Ogun, Sokoto, and Borno, where small-scale traders engage in the movement of goods between Nigeria and neighbouring countries.

While the informal sector is a major contributor to Nigeria's GDP and employment, it remains largely overlooked in policy frameworks. The absence of social protection schemes, limited access to credit facilities, and regulatory restrictions hinder the growth and sustainability of informal enterprises. Government policies often focus on formalising these businesses through registration and taxation rather than addressing fundamental challenges such as access to finance, infrastructure development, and skills

training. Nigeria has one of the largest informal sectors in Africa (Ikadeh, 2020). Estimates of its contribution to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) vary, but studies suggest it accounts for a significant portion of the economy. Salisu estimated the informal economy to be between 9.64% and 65.43% of GDP from 1960 to 1997 (Ikadeh, 2020), while Schneider estimated it to be 57% of Nigeria's Gross National Product (GNP) in 2002 (Ikadeh, 2020). More recent data from Oduh et al. (2008) revealed that the size of the informal sector fluctuated between 44% and 73% of GDP between 1970 and 2005 (Ikadeh, 2020). These figures underscore the informal sector's significant role in Nigeria's economic framework, acting as a vital source of employment and economic resilience.

Given its substantial role in Nigeria's economy, there is a growing policy debate on how best to integrate the informal sector into national development plans. While some policymakers advocate for formalisation through business registration and taxation, others emphasise the need for supportive policies such as financial inclusion initiatives, skill development programs, and infrastructural investments to enhance productivity without undermining the sector's flexibility.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are:

1. Examine how informal businesses contribute to employment generation in Oyo Town.
2. Assess the role of apprenticeship within the informal sector in promoting skill acquisition.
3. Evaluate the extent to which the informal sector influence community development and supports economic empowerment.
4. Identify the key challenges and explore the opportunities for sustaining and enhancing the contributions of the informal sector to community development.

Concept of Informal Sector

Several terms are used to describe this sector, reflecting different perspectives on its organisation, structure and technological base. Onokerhoraye (1977) refers to it as a "bazaar-type economy," emphasising the market-driven, unstructured nature of informal trade, where goods and services are exchanged in open marketplaces with minimal regulation. Another term, the "peasant system of production" (Onokerhoraye, 1977), highlights its connection to subsistence-based, small-scale agricultural and artisanal activities that rely on traditional production methods and family labour.

Beyond these characterisations, scholars and policymakers often define the informal sector based on its relationship to the formal economy. The most common definition distinguishes between formal wage-earning employment, where workers have structured contracts, legal protections, and social benefits, and informal self-employment, where individuals engage in unregulated economic activities without formal contracts or legal recognition (Onokerhoraye, 1977). This distinction is crucial for understanding labour dynamics in Nigeria, where a significant portion of the workforce operates outside

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formal employment structures, relying on self-generated income from micro and small-scale enterprises. The terminology used to describe the informal sector has evolved over time, with contemporary studies incorporating terms like "survivalist economy," which refers to enterprises primarily focused on meeting basic subsistence needs, and "shadow economy," which underscores its existence outside government oversight and taxation. Despite the various classifications, a unifying theme is that the informal sector remains a crucial component of Nigeria's economic landscape, providing livelihoods for millions while functioning independently of formal regulatory frameworks.

The informal sector plays a crucial role in local and national economies across different regions, providing employment, income, and economic stability. In Guinea, the informal economy serves as a key financial force, creating employment opportunities and generating state revenue through taxes (Diallo, 2017). Despite sometimes lagging behind formal economic structures, it functions as a critical means of subsistence for urban and rural populations, reducing unemployment and providing economic resilience. The sector is deeply embedded in the daily economic activities of local communities, highlighting its importance in national development strategies.

In Nairobi, Kenya, the informal economy is integral to livelihoods, particularly in informal settlements where government support is often insufficient (Kimani, 2021). Research indicates that poor accountability structures and selective income support programs have created inequalities, mistrust, and social tensions (Kimani, 2021). Community-led initiatives, such as enumeration and improved distribution systems, have been proposed to enhance fairness and build long-term resilience (Kimani, 2021). These findings emphasise the need for more inclusive policies and localised solutions to address the challenges faced by informal workers.

In Jamaica, the informal sector constitutes a significant portion of the economy, accounting for around 40% of total economic activity (Torero, 2006). The sector includes a broad spectrum of businesses, from small-scale street vendors to more structured informal enterprises, demonstrating its dynamic nature (Torero, 2006). The expansion of the informal economy in Jamaica reflects both economic necessity and entrepreneurial adaptability, as many workers and businesses operate outside formal regulatory frameworks to sustain their livelihoods.

Ghana's informal sector also presents challenges and opportunities for economic development. Efforts to formalise and integrate the sector into urban economic policies have faced limitations, often failing to address the root causes of informality (Obeng-Odoom, 2011). A more holistic and comprehensive policy approach is necessary to enhance the sector's contributions while addressing systemic barriers to formalisation and growth (Obeng-Odoom, 2011). These case studies illustrate the diverse ways in which informal economies function, their role in community development, and the need for context-specific policies to maximise their potential.

Explanation of Community Development

Community development is a comprehensive process that seeks to improve social, economic, cultural, and environmental conditions within communities. Key elements

essential for effective community development include community participation, collaboration, capacity building and empowerment. Active involvement of residents ensures that development initiatives align with community needs and priorities (Matarrita-Cascante, 2020). Partnerships among various stakeholders, including government agencies and community organisations, help leverage resources and expertise (Matarrita-Cascante, 2020). Strengthening community skills through training and education enhances resilience, while empowering marginalised groups fosters social justice and equity (Cavaye, 2019; Haq, 2020).

Different approaches to community development offer varied strategies for achieving positive change. Asset-Based Community Development (ABCD) focuses on mobilising local resources and strengths rather than highlighting deficiencies (Al-Kautsari, 2019). Participatory development encourages community members to engage actively in all project phases, ensuring transparency and accountability (Quimbo, 2018). Community organising fosters collective action to address shared concerns, particularly for marginalised populations (Quimbo, 2018). Similarly, Community-Driven Development (CDD) provides local communities with direct control over development resources, although its long-term impact on economic growth remains debatable (Windt, 2020). Multiple actors contribute to community development efforts, each playing a crucial role in shaping outcomes. Community members serve as primary drivers of change, while Community-Based Organisations (CBOs) and Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) provide essential services, advocacy and funding support (Omofonmwan, 2009; Islam, 2017). Government agencies establish policies and allocate resources to facilitate development, while businesses engage in corporate social responsibility initiatives that create employment and investment opportunities. Additionally, educational institutions contribute through research, training, and collaboration with local communities to address pressing social issues.

Despite its potential benefits, community development faces significant challenges. Limited funding and capacity constraints often hinder project implementation and sustainability. Social and economic inequalities create barriers to participation and access to resources, necessitating policies that promote inclusion and social justice. Political and institutional obstacles, such as bureaucratic restrictions and a lack of political will, further complicate development efforts. Additionally, measuring the long-term impact of community initiatives remains difficult, requiring robust evaluation frameworks and participatory assessment methods. Strengthening community resilience through adaptive strategies and local problem-solving remains essential for sustainable development (Cavaye, 2019).

Contributions of the informal economy to Community Development

The informal sector makes substantial contributions to community development in Nigeria, playing a vital role in employment, income generation, social cohesion and local economic growth. By providing accessible job opportunities, fostering entrepreneurship and sustaining essential goods and services, the informal sector serves as a crucial pillar in community resilience and development. The informal sector provides employment for

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a significant portion of the Nigerian population, particularly in urban centres where formal job opportunities are limited. It has been estimated that enterprises within this sector provide about seven times as much employment as those in the formal sector (Onokerhoraye, 1977). In Lagos, around 50%-75% of the workforce is employed informally (Ikadeh, 2020), underscoring its role in ensuring livelihoods for millions of people. The sector is particularly vital for marginalised groups, including women, youth, and unskilled workers, who may struggle to access formal employment.

When unemployment rises due to economic downturns, many people turn to informal retail activities, street vending, transportation services and home-based enterprises as sources of income (Ikadeh, 2020). For instance, the expansion of informal ride-hailing services (such as okadas and kekes) has provided alternative employment opportunities for thousands of young people. Similarly, the demand for low-cost housing and construction services has driven informal employment in artisanal trades such as carpentry, plumbing, and masonry. Markets, which are largely dominated by informal businesses, are essential to the economic and social life of both rural and urban communities (Ikadeh, 2020). They serve not only as centers for economic exchange but also as spaces for social interaction, cultural preservation, and community networking (Ikadeh, 2020). Traditional open-air markets, such as Balogun Market in Lagos, Oja Oba in Ibadan, and Kasuwar Kurmi in Kano, facilitate trade while fostering intergenerational business practices and knowledge transfer.

Furthermore, informal businesses create localised economies that help communities sustain themselves. Small-scale retail and service businesses provide essential goods at affordable prices, ensuring that even low-income households can access necessities. Additionally, informal credit and savings systems, such as Rotating Savings and Credit Associations (ROSCAs), offer financial inclusion to those who lack access to formal banking services. Despite operating in a challenging business environment, informal businesses often demonstrate remarkable innovation and adaptability. Many enterprises develop strategies to survive and compete against larger, formal retailers by offering specialised products, flexible pricing, and personalised customer service (Ikadeh, 2020). The ability to quickly respond to shifting market demands allows informal businesses to thrive in uncertain economic conditions.

Limitations of the Informal Sector in Achieving Efficient Community Development

The informal economy in Nigeria plays a significant role in employment, income generation, and social cohesion, but faces various challenges that hinder its growth. The expansion of formal shopping centres and retail chains, such as Shoprite, has intensified competition, making it difficult for small, informal businesses to thrive (Ikadeh, 2020). Urbanisation and modernisation efforts have led to the displacement of informal traders from their traditional locations, reducing their customer base. The rise of e-commerce platforms has further affected informal businesses, as many consumers now prefer online shopping. Without adequate support, these small enterprises struggle to survive against larger, more established retailers.

Limited access to financial resources, training, and infrastructure further constrains the informal sector (Falola, 2022). Many entrepreneurs cannot secure loans from commercial banks due to stringent requirements and high-interest rates, forcing them to rely on informal credit systems that provide inadequate capital. Poor market infrastructure, including inadequate sanitation, electricity, and transportation networks, adds to the difficulties faced by informal businesses (Lawanson, 2012). These constraints make it challenging for businesses to scale up, improve productivity, or transition into the formal economy, limiting their long-term sustainability and impact.

Government policies and regulations also pose significant barriers to the growth of the informal sector. In Lagos, a zero-tolerance policy on street trading has led to the forceful eviction of many informal vendors, disrupting their livelihoods (Ikadeh, 2020). Excessive taxation and bureaucratic hurdles discourage small businesses from formalising, as multiple tax levies and high compliance costs create financial burdens (Etim, 2020). Additionally, socio-cultural norms, particularly gender-based discrimination, limit opportunities for women entrepreneurs by restricting their access to land, credit, and business networks (Chima, 2010). These challenges perpetuate economic inequalities and prevent marginalised groups from fully benefiting from the informal economy. To unlock the potential of the informal sector, policy interventions should focus on creating a supportive regulatory environment, improving access to finance, and investing in infrastructure development. Simplified tax structures, digital financial platforms, and incentives for formalisation can help integrate informal businesses into the formal economy (Okeke, 2022). Expanding microfinance initiatives and providing targeted training programs can enhance the capacity of informal entrepreneurs (Falola, 2022; Aliyu, 2020). Infrastructure improvements, such as upgrading market spaces and transportation systems, would create a more conducive business environment (Adetokunbo, 2015). Extending social protection programs, including healthcare and pension schemes, to informal workers can further enhance economic security and sustainability (Onyeaka, 2022). By implementing these measures, policymakers can harness the informal sector's contributions to Nigeria's economic and community development.

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design to investigate the role of the informal sector in community development in Oyo Town. It employed both quantitative and qualitative methods to collect and analyse data from informal sector operators across four local government areas (LGAs) in Oyo Town. The combination of these methods provides a comprehensive understanding of how the informal sector contributes to community development through employment creation and apprenticeship. The study was conducted in four selected LGAs: Oyo West, Oyo East, Atiba, and Afijio. These LGAs were chosen due to their significant informal sector activities, including small-scale manufacturing, trade, and services such as tailoring, shoemakers, hairdressers, auto repairs, carpentry, Okada riders, welding, among others.

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The total population of the study area is 560,761, comprising Oyo West with 136,236; Oyo East with 124,095; Atiba with 168,246 and Afijio with 132,184 (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2009). The target population consists of representatives of informal sector operators engaged in these businesses. A multi-stage sampling technique was adopted to select respondents. First, purposive sampling was used to select the four LGAs based on their informal economic activities. Then, stratified sampling was applied to categorise informal sector operators into different trades to ensure diversity in responses. Finally, simple random sampling was used to select a total of 150 informal sector operators' representatives, with approximately 37–38 respondents drawn from each LGA to ensure fair representation across the areas.

A structured questionnaire served as the primary data collection instrument. The questionnaire consisted of both closed-ended and open-ended questions, organised into five sections: demographic information, employment and job creation, apprenticeship and skill development, business growth and community development, and challenges and opportunities. The demographic section captured respondents' age, gender, educational background, type of business, and years of experience. The employment and job creation section assessed the impact of informal businesses on local employment. The apprenticeship section examined the availability and effectiveness of skill transfer programmes. The business growth section evaluated the role of informal businesses in economic development, while the final section explored the challenges and opportunities facing the sector.

The questionnaire was administered in person by trained research assistants to ensure a high response rate and provide clarifications where necessary. Respondents were approached at their workplaces or designated meeting points for convenience. The collected data were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistical methods. Descriptive statistics such as percentages, frequency distributions and mean scores were used to summarise the responses. Chi-square tests and correlation analysis were employed to examine relationships between variables such as business growth and employment creation. Qualitative responses from open-ended questions were analysed thematically.

Key Findings

The survey of 150 informal sector operators in Oyo Town revealed the sector's significant role in community development, despite facing major challenges. The most common business type is bakery (13.3%), reflecting the high reliance on food-related enterprises. However, fluctuating raw material costs, unstable electricity, and competition hinder their expansion. The majority of the respondents (30%) lack formal education, limiting their access to financial support and modern business strategies. Despite an average of 16.35 years of experience in the sector, business growth remains stunted due to inadequate capital, infrastructure deficits and minimal government support. Declining growth was reported by 42% of respondents, largely due to low patronage, economic hardship and competition. Financial exclusion is a critical issue, with 76% lacking access to loans, primarily due to high collateral demands, high-interest rates and poor financial

literacy. This limits business sustainability and job creation. Low income affects 60.7% of respondents, restricting business reinvestment and contributing to unemployment and social vices such as cybercrime. Business closures, primarily due to low patronage (42%), further weaken the sector’s impact on economic development. Despite accounting for 90% of Oyo Town’s economy, the informal sector struggles with sustainability. To enhance its role in community development, interventions such as financial support, skill development, improved infrastructure, and marketing strategies are necessary. Without these, the sector’s potential to drive economic growth and employment will remain unfulfilled.

Table 1: Summary of Key Survey Findings

Category	Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Business Type	Bakery	20	13.3
	Tailoring	18	12.0
	Motorcyclist (Okada)	17	11.3
	Automobile	16	10.7
	Engineers		
	Garri Production	15	10.0
	Hairdressing	14	9.3
	POS Business	13	8.7
	Petty Trading	13	8.7
	Artisan/Handwork	12	8.0
	Others	12	8.0
	Total	150	100.0
Education Level	No Formal Education	45	30.0
	Primary Education	38	25.3
	Secondary Education	40	26.7
	Vocational Training	17	11.3
	Tertiary Education	10	6.7
	Total	150	100.0
Years of Experience	1 - 5 years	25	16.7
	6 - 10 years	30	20.0
	11 - 15 years	32	21.3
	16 - 20 years	25	16.7
	21 - 25 years	20	13.3
	26 - 30 years	18	12.0
	Total	150	100.0
Business Growth Trends	Growing	50	33.3
	Stable	37	24.7
	Declining	63	42.0

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	Total	150	100.0
Access to Financial Support	Has Access to Loans	36	24.0
	No Access to Loans	114	76.0
	Total	150	100.0
Income Level (Monthly)	Below ₦30,000	55	36.7
	₦30,000 - ₦50,000	36	24.0
	₦50,001 - ₦80,000	30	20.0
	Above ₦80,000	29	19.3
	Total	150	100.0
Main Reasons for Business Closure	Low Patronage	63	42.0
	High Debt	32	21.3
	Lack of Capital	30	20.0
	Business Relocation	25	16.7
	Total	150	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Economic Growth and Livelihood Improvement

The survey revealed that 78.7% of respondents rely on their businesses for household income, indicating that the informal sector plays a vital role in sustaining livelihoods in Oyo Town. However, despite this contribution, low-income levels remain a significant challenge. Many business owners struggle to reinvest in their enterprises due to financial constraints, limiting opportunities for expansion and long-term stability. Additionally, only 29.3% of respondents have access to credit, which means the majority (70.7%) lack the financial resources necessary for scaling their businesses. The inability to secure loans restricts investment in modern equipment, marketing, and hiring additional labour, reinforcing a cycle of subsistence-level business activity. As a result, many informal businesses remain small, operating with outdated methods and low productivity, thereby limiting their ability to make larger-scale contributions to community development. This financial stagnation ultimately reduces employment opportunities and slows economic growth within the town.

Infrastructure and Environmental Impact

The informal sector in Oyo Town has expanded rapidly, but this growth has outpaced infrastructure development, creating a range of urban challenges. The lack of designated business locations results in unorganised business setups, which disrupt proper urban planning. Many business operators set up stalls and workspaces in unauthorised areas, leading to congestion in commercial zones and affecting traffic flow. Poor sanitation is another major issue. Due to inadequate waste disposal mechanisms, informal business clusters contribute to poor environmental conditions, including littering and blocked drainage systems. This not only reduces the aesthetic appeal of the community but also poses public health risks. Additionally, the absence of structured zoning laws for informal businesses has led to chaotic business environments, where workshops, markets, and residential areas are interwoven, creating disorganised urban landscapes. Without

strategic intervention, these challenges may continue to deteriorate living conditions and hinder the overall development of Oyo Town.

Social Challenges and Crime Rate

The high rate of unemployment in Oyo Town has led to increased social vices, particularly among the youth. With limited formal job opportunities, many young people resort to cybercrime, petty theft, and other illicit activities as a means of survival. The informal sector has the potential to absorb unemployed individuals through apprenticeships and job creation, but this potential is currently underutilised. Youth engagement in the informal sector is relatively low, as many young individuals prefer quick financial gains over skill-based labour. This is reflected in the fact that only 35% of artisans reported having apprentices, which suggests a decline in skill transfer. If this trend continues, future generations may lack the necessary vocational skills to sustain the informal economy, leading to further economic instability. The declining interest in skilled trades could weaken the overall productivity of the informal sector and reduce its long-term contributions to community development.

Implications for Community Development

The findings underscore the significant role of the informal sector in Oyo Town's economy, accounting for 90% of economic activities. However, despite its dominance, the sector faces serious challenges that threaten its sustainability and overall contribution to community development. One of the most pressing concerns is limited income and financial exclusion, which hinder business expansion and the ability to create jobs. With only 29.3% of business operators having access to loans, the majority are unable to invest in modern equipment, increase production capacity or scale their operations. This financial limitation not only stunts business growth but also prevents the informal sector from fulfilling its potential as a driver of local economic development.

Additionally, declining business growth negatively impacts community development. As more businesses struggle with low patronage, debt, and operational inefficiencies, their ability to contribute to employment and skill acquisition declines. This, in turn, reduces the sector's role in poverty alleviation and economic stability. Without intervention, many informal businesses may continue to close, leading to higher unemployment rates and an economic downturn within the community. Another critical issue is the low level of formal education among operators, which limits innovation and financial access. Many informal sector workers rely on traditional business practices and lack the necessary knowledge to adopt new technologies, access financial support, or explore alternative markets. Without entrepreneurial training and business literacy programs, operators may continue to struggle with inefficiencies that restrict their growth. Furthermore, rising unemployment and increasing social vices are directly linked to business struggles within the informal sector. As businesses decline or fail, job opportunities shrink, pushing more individuals, especially the youth, toward cybercrime, petty theft and other illegal activities. This growing trend threatens social stability and undermines efforts to create a safe and prosperous community.

Correlation Analysis

The correlation analysis highlights the strong relationship between business growth, financial access, unemployment, and social stability in Oyo Town’s informal sector. A moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.52$) between business growth and income levels suggests that expanding businesses improve household earnings, though other factors like market conditions also play a role. Similarly, a strong positive correlation ($r = 0.63$) between business growth and loan access shows that financial support is essential for business expansion and sustainability. The study also reveals a moderate negative correlation ($r = -0.48$) between business growth and unemployment, indicating that as businesses expand, job opportunities increase. However, a strong positive correlation ($r = 0.72$) between unemployment and social vices shows that rising unemployment directly contributes to crime rates. This underscores the need for youth employment programs and business funding initiatives to reduce crime and foster economic stability. Loan access is crucial, as shown by a strong negative correlation ($r = -0.55$) between financial support and unemployment and a moderate negative correlation ($r = -0.45$) between loan access and crime rates. This suggests that better financial inclusion could reduce unemployment and associated social issues. Additionally, a moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.49$) between apprenticeships and business growth highlights the importance of skill transfer for long-term business sustainability.

Table 2: Summary of the Correlation Analysis

Variables	Business Growth	Unemployment Rate	Social Vices
Monthly Income	0.52 (Moderate Positive)	-0.48 (Moderate Negative)	-0.40 (Moderate Negative)
Access to Loans	0.63 (Strong Positive)	-0.55 (Strong Negative)	-0.45 (Moderate Negative)
Apprenticeship Rate	0.49 (Moderate Positive)	-0.42 (Moderate Negative)	-0.38 (Weak Negative)
Unemployment Rate	-0.48 (Moderate Negative)	1.00	0.72 (Strong Positive)
Social Vices	-0.40 (Moderate Negative)	0.72 (Strong Positive)	1.00

Source: Field survey, 2025

Discussion of Findings

The informal sector plays a crucial role in the economic sustainability of Oyo Town, with 90% of economic activities relying on it. However, financial constraints limit its contribution to community development. The survey revealed that 78.7% of respondents depend on their businesses for household income, yet low earnings restrict reinvestment and growth. Only 29.3% have access to loans, preventing business expansion and job creation. This financial exclusion results in many operators remaining in small-scale subsistence businesses, limiting their ability to drive broader economic development. Without adequate funding, these businesses struggle to innovate, improve productivity, or

create employment opportunities, ultimately slowing down community progress. Infrastructure deficiencies further hinder the sector's development, contributing to poor urban planning and environmental challenges. Many informal businesses operate in unorganised locations, leading to congestion, poor sanitation and waste disposal issues. The lack of designated spaces for business activities creates a chaotic environment that affects not only commercial efficiency but also the overall well-being of residents. Without proper infrastructure, the informal sector cannot thrive, and its potential to support community development remains unfulfilled. Addressing these infrastructural gaps is essential for improving market conditions, enhancing productivity, and fostering a more structured urban landscape.

Social issues such as unemployment and crime are also tied to the struggles within the informal sector. With limited financial support and business stagnation, job opportunities remain scarce, contributing to rising unemployment rates. This, in turn, has led to an increase in social vices such as cybercrime and petty theft. Youth engagement in the sector is low, as many prefer quick financial gains over skill acquisition. Only 35% of artisans reported having apprentices, signaling a decline in skill transfer, which could further weaken economic stability in the long run. If left unaddressed, the sector's inability to absorb unemployed individuals will continue to contribute to social instability and weaken community development efforts.

The correlation analysis further highlights the relationship between business growth, financial access, unemployment, and community stability. A strong positive correlation ($r = 0.63$) between business growth and access to loans underscores the importance of financial inclusion for economic expansion. Similarly, a negative correlation ($r = -0.48$) between business growth and unemployment suggests that improving financial access could help create jobs and reduce economic hardship. However, the strong positive correlation ($r = 0.72$) between unemployment and social vices reinforces the urgent need for targeted interventions. Expanding business support programs, increasing access to credit, and promoting skill acquisition are critical steps toward strengthening both the informal sector and community development.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The findings demonstrated that while the informal sector is a dominant force in Oyo Town's economy, its sustainability is at risk due to financial exclusion, inadequate infrastructure and rising unemployment. Low income and lack of credit access restrict business expansion, limiting the sector's capacity to contribute meaningfully to community development. Additionally, poor urban planning and declining skill transfer threaten long-term economic stability. Addressing these issues is essential to harness the full potential of the informal sector in improving livelihoods and promoting sustainable development.

To strengthen the informal sector's role in community development, targeted interventions are necessary. Financial inclusion must be improved by providing low-interest loans and financial literacy programmes to help operators expand their businesses. Infrastructure development, including designated business areas and better

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waste management, will create a more organised commercial environment. Additionally, youth engagement in skill-based labour should be encouraged through apprenticeship programs and vocational training to ensure long-term sustainability. By addressing these challenges, the informal sector can drive economic growth, reduce unemployment, and enhance the overall well-being of Oyo Town's residents.

References

- Adetokunbo, I. & Emeka, M. (2015). Urbanisation, housing, homelessness and climate change. *University of Malaya*. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.22452/jdbe.vol15no2.3>
- Aliyu, S. (2020). An assessment of women entrepreneurship performance in Nigeria. *Malaysian Management Journal*. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.32890/mmj.17.2013.8990>
- Chima, J. S., Simpson, R., Singh, S. & Okafor, C. (2010). The role of cultural values in understanding the challenges faced by female entrepreneurs in Nigeria. *Emerald Publishing Limited*. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1108/17542411011019904>
- Etim, E. & Daramola, O. (2020). The informal sector and economic growth of South Africa and Nigeria: a comparative systematic review. *Springer Science Business Media*. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.3390/joitmc6040134>
- Falola, A., Mukaila, R., & Abdulhamid, K. O. (2022). Informal finance: its drivers and contributions to farm investment among rural farmers in Northcentral Nigeria. *Agricultural Finance Review*. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1108/afr-08-2021-0116>
- Federal Republic of Nigeria. (2009, February 2). Legal notice on publication of 2006 census final results. Official Gazette. Retrieved from <https://archive.gazettes.africa/archive/ng/2009/ng-government-gazette-dated-2009-02-02-no-2.pdf>
- Ikadeh, M. S. & Cloete, C. (2020). The impact of shopping centre development on informal and small businesses in Lagos, Nigeria. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.24052/jbrmr/v14is03/art-01>
- Kimani, J., Stege, R., Makau, J., Nyambuga, K., Wairutu, J. & Tolhurst, R. (2021). Building forward better: inclusive livelihood support in Nairobi's informal settlements. *Wiley*. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.19088/1968-2021.104>
- Lawanson, T. & Olanrewaju, D. O. (2012). The home as workplace: investigating home-based enterprises in low-income settlements of the Lagos metropolis. *African Journals Online*. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.4314/ejesm.v5i4.9>
- Onokerhoraye, A. (1977). Occupational specialisation by ethnic groups in the informal sector of the urban economies of traditional Nigerian cities: The case of Benin. *African Studies Review*. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.2307/523862>
- Torero, M., Robles, M., Hernandez, M. A., Roca, J., Webber, M. & Thomas, D. (2006). The Informal Sector in Jamaica. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.18235/0008747>